

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE STRUCTURE OF MAXILLOFACIAL DISEASES OF PATIENTS
WITH NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL DISTURBANCES AND
PECULIARITIES OF TEMPORARY DISABILITY EXAMINATION**

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Abstract:

According to statistics, every year in the Republic of Tatarstan 62±0.5% of patients with neuropsychological disturbances undergo treatment of diseases of dental tissue and mucous tunic under general anesthesia, whereas disease recurrence rate is quite high (on average, 76.8%) [1,2,3]. This category of patients has certain peculiarities: psychoemotional response to procedures; difficulty in adequate mouth assessment; impossibility of diagnostic study of maxillofacial area; the dentist lacks skills of communication with this group of patients; failure to maintain proper oral hygiene by the parent, the guardian, the patient himself/herself; impossibility of final diagnosing of dental disease without general anesthesia[3]. The source of information were cases of patients with neuropsychological disturbances who received treatment in the maxillofacial departments of specialized hospital, as well as clear temporary disability cases. The research material was subjected to statistical processing using the methods of parametric and nonparametric analysis in accordance with the results of testing the compared sets for normality of distribution. According to the results of the study carried out among the patients residing in the Republic of Tatarstan for the period of 2013-2017, the authors revealed the prevalence of dental diseases among patients with neuropsychological disturbances receiving treatment in the maxillofacial surgery departments, such as caries extending into dentine (K02.1), acute and chronic periodontitis (K04.5), acute pulpitis (K04.0). There was revealed a statistically significant correlation between prevalence and intensity of acute pulpitis and periodontitis and underlying medical condition: acute pulpitis is more peculiar to the patients with other diseases, and acute periodontitis – to the patients with intellectual disability. The high level of prevalence and intensity of dental diseases was revealed among the studied patients over a period of 5 years. This enables us to claim the influence of poor oral hygiene, effect of drugs that the patients have to take due to comorbidities, as well as somatic pathology worsened by poor dental health of this group of patients. Besides, the authors have studied the peculiarities of examination of temporary disability due to nursing a family member in the studied group of patients.

Ключевые слова: dentistry, temporary disability examination, maxillofacial diseases, neuropsychological disturbances..

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Please cite this article in press KANGA Yao et al., Cytotoxicity And Antibacterial Activity Of The 70%Ethanollic Extract Of The Stem Bark Of Piptadeniastrum Africanum Hook (Fabaceae)., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Diseases of the nervous system and neuropsychological disturbances remain quite common in Russia: 765.3-1,681.3 people per 100 thous. Children [1, 2, 3]. Oral cavity sanitation in the studied group of patients involves some problems due to certain clinical aspects of neuropsychological disease and low level of compliance. According to statistics, every year in the Republic of Tatarstan $62 \pm 0.5\%$ of patients with neuropsychological disturbances undergo treatment of diseases of dental tissue and mucous tunic under general anesthesia, whereas disease recurrence rate is quite high (on average, 76.8%). This category of patients has certain peculiarities: psychoemotional response to procedures; difficulty in adequate mouth assessment; impossibility of diagnostic study of maxillofacial area; the dentist lacks skills of communication with this group of patients; failure to maintain proper oral hygiene by the parent, the guardian, the patient himself/herself; impossibility of final diagnosing of dental disease without general anesthesia [4,5,6].

Temporary disability examination is a type of medical care aimed at assessment of the patient's general health, the quality and the efficiency of treatment, the ability to work, setting the period of temporary disability. Furthermore, the temporary disability is applicable in case of nursing the family member. There are many reasons that can affect the duration of temporary disability among patients with neuropsychological disturbances suffering from maxillofacial diseases, however, in the modern literature, the issues of structure of maxillofacial morbidity, as far as the studied group of patients is concerned, peculiarities of their treatment and

temporary disability examination, are not fully disclosed [6,7,8,9].

Research objective:

Assessment of prevalence of dental diseases among patients with neuropsychological disturbances and study of the peculiarities of temporary disability examination during oral cavity sanitation under general anesthesia.

MATERIAL AND RESEARCH METHODS:

The sources of information were cases of patients with neuropsychological disturbances who received treatment in the maxillofacial department of specialized hospital, as well as clear temporary disability cases. The research material was subjected to statistical processing using the methods of parametric and nonparametric analysis in accordance with the results of testing the compared sets for normality of distribution. The initial information was accumulated, corrected, systematized and the results were visualized in Microsoft Office Excel 2016 spreadsheets. The statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 23.

RESULTS:

There were examined 128 patients who underwent treatment in the years from 2013 to 2017, including in 2013 – 22 cases (17.2%), in 2014 – 24 cases (18.8%), in 2015 – 27 cases (21.1%), in 2016 – 23 cases (18.0%), and in 2017 – 32 cases (25.0%). There was almost equal quantity of male and female patients, 50.8 and 49.2 correspondingly. Distribution of patients with neuropsychological disturbances, who received treatment under general anesthesia, by gender depending on year of assessment is given in the Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of patients with neuropsychological disturbances, who received treatment under general anesthesia, by gender depending on year of assessment

Year of assessment	Gender			
	Male		Female	
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
2013	13	59.1	9	40.9
2014	11	45.8	13	54.2
2015	15	55.6	12	44.4
2016	10	43.5	13	56.5
2017	16	50.0	16	50.0
TOTAL:	65	50.8	63	49.2

When the distribution of patients by gender taking into account year of assessment was studied, the differences were statistically insignificant ($p=0.811$), per cent of male patients varied from 43.5% in 2016 to 59.1% in 2013.

The studied patients were from 15 to 66 years of age; median age was 24 years of age; and interquartile range from 18 to 33 years of age. The median age of studied male patients was 24 years of age (Q₁-Q₃: 18-35 years of age), female patients – 24 years of age (Q₁-Q₃: 20.5-30.5). The differences were statistically insignificant (p=0.83). Distribution of patients by age groups depending on gender is given in the Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of patients by age groups depending on gender

Age	Gender				Total	
	Male		Female			
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
Under 20	23	35.4	15	23.8	38	29.7
20-29	20	30.8	31	49.2	51	39.8
30-39	14	21.5	11	17.5	25	19.5
40-49	5	7.7	1	1.6	6	4.7
50-59	3	4.6	3	4.8	6	4.7
Over 60	0	0.0	2	3.2	2	1.6
TOTAL:	65	100.0	63	100.0	128	100.0

According to the data obtained, there was more male patients under 19 years of age (35.4%), whereas the female patients at the age of 20-29 (49.2%). The per cent of patients over 30 years of age was rather low in both age groups. When male and female patients were compared taking into account their age, the differences were statistically insignificant (p=0.107).

The important factor was that the studied patients suffered from certain diseases; their structure is given in the Figure 1

Fig. 1 Structure of the studied group of patients taking into account underlying medical condition.

Based on the data obtained, as far as the structure of the studied group is concerned, the major part are cases of cerebral palsy (35.9%); intellectual disability takes the second place (28.1%); and schizophrenia takes the third place (10.2%). We have also considered the age structure of the studied group depending on whether they suffered from one or another disease (Table 30).

Table 3: Comparing distribution of the studied patients by age depending on underlying medical condition

Nosological group	Age at last birthday							
	<20		20-29		30-39		40 and >	
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
Cerebral palsy	14	30.4	15	32.6	15	32.6	2	4.3
Intellectual disability	10	27.8	20	55.6	3	8.3	3	8.3
Schizophrenia	5	38.5	4	30.8	2	15.4	2	15.4
Other	9	27.3	12	36.4	5	15.2	7	21.2

In accordance with the data obtained, there was no significant difference of patients by age depending on the underlying medical condition ($p=0.077$). The medical conditions, which formed the major part in the studied group, were defined by young age of the studied patients: The rate of patients under 30 years of age was more than 63% in case of cerebral palsy and up to 83.4% in case of intellectual disability. The rate of patients over 40 years of age was higher in the group of patients suffering from other diseases (21.2%). Similar age of patients suffering from different diseases allows not to take into account the age factor, when nosological groups are compared.

The next step was to study the prevalence of dental diseases taking into account the gender, age, and nosological group of the patients.

Upon dental examination under general anesthesia and oral cavity sanitation of patients with neuropsychological disturbances, it was found that caries extending into dentine was peculiar to 39 patients (K02.1), that is 30.5% of the time, acute and chronic pulpitis (K04.0) – to 31 patients (24.2%), acute and chronic periodontitis (K04.5) – to 99 patients (77.3%). We have studied the correlation between the acute and chronic forms of dental diseases and different factors. The prevalence of dental diseases among patients depending on their age was given in the Table 4.

Table 4: Comparing the prevalence of dental diseases among patients depending on their age

Dental diseases	Age at last birthday								p
	<20		20-29		30-39		40 and >		
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	
Caries, incl.:	12	31.6	13	25.5	12	48.0	2	14.3	0.113
- acute;	9	23.7	10	19.6	11	44.0	2	14.3	0.089
- chronic	7	18.4	8	15.7	4	16.0	2	14.3	0.981
Pulpitis, incl.:	11	28.9	10	19.6	7	28.0	3	21.4	0.727
- acute;	10	26.3	8	15.7	7	28.0	2	14.3	0.453
- chronic	4	10.5	5	9.8	1	4.0	1	7.1	0.805
Periodontitis, incl.:	26	68.4	43	84.3	17	68.0	13	92.9	0.098
- acute;	18	47.4	35	68.6	15	60.0	11	78.6	0.109
- chronic	19	50.0	32	62.7	14	56.0	9	64.3	0.629

According to the Pearson's chi-square test, there were no statistically significant differences of the prevalence of dental diseases taking into account the age of studied patients ($p>0.05$ in all cases). Whereas, it is worth mentioning that the acute caries was more peculiar to the patients at the age of 30-39, that is 44.0%. In other age groups this rate was less than 24%. The significance level of differences was close to critical ($p=0.089$).

Then, the prevalence of dental diseases taking into account the underlying medical condition was studied (see Table 5).

Table 5: Comparing the prevalence of dental diseases among patients depending on their underlying medical condition

Dental diseases	Underlying medical condition								p
	Cerebral palsy		Intellectual disability		Schizophrenia		Other		
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	
Caries, incl.:	14	30.4	7	19.4	5	38.5	13	39.4	0.296
- acute;	12	26.1	4	11.1	3	23.1	13	39.4	0.06
- chronic	4	8.7	7	19.4	4	30.8	6	18.2	0.234
Pulpitis, incl.:	11	23.9	2	5.6	3	23.1	15	45.5	0.002*
- acute;	10	21.7	2	5.6	2	15.4	13	39.4	0.007*
- chronic	6	13.0	1	2.8	1	7.7	3	9.1	0.435
Periodontitis, incl.:	36	78.3	34	94.4	10	76.9	19	57.6	0.004*
- acute;	29	63.0	31	86.1	6	46.2	13	39.4	0.001*
- chronic	29	63.0	23	63.9	8	61.5	14	42.4	0.227

* - the differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)

Based on the data obtained, the differences of prevalence of dental diseases, such as pulpitis and periodontitis ($p=0.002$ and $p=0.004$), were statistically significant. The assessment of prevalence rate of acute and chronic pulpitis proved that the found differences resulted from the higher rate of acute pulpitis among the patients suffering from other diseases (39.4%) and cerebral palsy (21.7%) and its lower rate among the patients suffering from intellectual disability (5.6%) ($p=0.007$). The prevalence of acute and chronic pulpitis depending

on the underlying medical condition is given in the Figure 2.

Besides, the differences, which were revealed when prevalence of periodontitis was studied, were due to the differences of prevalence of acute form of disease, which were higher among the patients with intellectual disability (86.1%) and lower among the patients with schizophrenia and other diseases (46.2% and 39.4%, correspondingly) ($p=0.001$). The prevalence of acute and chronic periodontitis is given in the Figure 3.

Fig.2. Comparing the prevalence of acute and chronic pulpitis depending on the underlying medical condition.

Fig. 3. Comparing the prevalence of acute and chronic pulpitis depending on the underlying medical condition.

Furthermore, the intensity of caries, pulpitis and periodontitis depending on the underlying medical condition was studied using one-way analysis of variance (Table 6).

Table 6

Intensity of dental disease among patients with different underlying medical condition

Dental diseases	Underlying medical condition				P
	Cerebral palsy	Intellectual disability	Schizophrenia	Other	
Acute caries	0.59±0.18	0.19±0.1	0.77±0.48	0.64±0.16	0.212
Chronic caries	0.09±0.04	0.19±0.06	0.31±0.13	0.27±0.12	0.249
Acute pulpitis	0.22±0.06	0.06±0.03	0.15±0.09	0.42±0.09	0.004*
Chronic pulpitis	0.15±0.06	0.03±0.03	0.08±0.08	0.15±0.09	0.44
Acute periodontitis	0.7±0.09	0.89±0.06	0.46±0.14	0.52±0.13	0.033*
Chronic periodontitis	1.93±0.43	1.31±0.23	2.08±0.89	0.88±0.22	0.154

* - the differences were statistically significant (p<0.05)

According to the analysis findings, there was a statistically significant difference of the number of teeth with acute pulpitis (p=0.004) and acute periodontitis (p=0.033). This is due to the fact that prevalence of pulpitis is substantially lower and prevalence of periodontitis is higher among the patients with intellectual disability. The intensity of acute pulpitis and acute periodontitis during various medical conditions are given in the Figure 4.

Thus, there was revealed a statistically significant correlation between prevalence and intensity of acute pulpitis and periodontitis and underlying medical condition: acute pulpitis is more peculiar to the patients with other diseases, and acute periodontitis – to the patients with intellectual disability. High prevalence and intensity of both diseases were peculiar to the patients with cerebral palsy.

Fig. 4. Comparing the prevalence of acute pulpitis and acute periodontitis depending on the underlying medical condition

The procedure for issuance of temporary disability leaves due to nursing a family member is approved by the Order No. 624H Concerning the Procedure for Issuance of Temporary Disability Leaves issued by the Ministry of Public Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation on June 29, 2011. In case of oral cavity sanitation of patients with neuropsychological disturbances under general anesthesia, the parent, the guardian or the legal representative of the patient has the right for temporary disability leave for the period of stay in the specialized hospital. However, when this occurs, temporary disability examination has certain peculiarities, specifically, the temporary disability leave due to nursing a family member is provided in the following cases:

- nursing a child under 7 years of age: for the whole period of outpatient treatment or joint stay in the medical organization during inpatient medical care;
- nursing a child at the age of 7-15: for the period of 15 days in each and every sickness case, unless longer period is stipulated by the medical commission, in case of joint stay of child and his/her family member (guardian, trustee, other relative) at the inpatient healthcare facility.
- nursing a disabled child under 18 years of age: for the whole period of joint stay in the medical organization during inpatient medical care.

Temporary disability leave is not granted for nursing: a family member over 15 years of age in case of

inpatient treatment; long-term care patient during remission. Besides, as far as the studied patients are concerned, during oral cavity sanitation the temporary disability leave was not granted to the patients over 18 years of age; the average period of stay in the maxillofacial department of specialized hospital was 2 ± 0.04 days.

CONCLUSIONS:

In the Republic of Tatarstan for the period of 2013-2017, we have found the prevalence of dental diseases among patients with neuropsychological disturbances receiving treatment in the maxillofacial surgery departments, such as caries extending into dentine (K02.1), acute and chronic periodontitis (K04.5), acute pulpitis (K04.0). We have revealed a statistically significant correlation between prevalence and intensity of acute pulpitis and periodontitis and underlying medical condition: acute pulpitis is more peculiar to the patients with other diseases, and acute periodontitis – to the patients with intellectual disability. The high level of prevalence and intensity of dental diseases was revealed among the studied patients over a period of 5 years. This enables us to claim the influence of poor oral hygiene due to the patient's or his/her guardian's inability to maintain it, the adverse effect of drugs that the patients have to take due to comorbidities, as well as somatic pathology worsened by poor dental health of this group of patients. Moreover, we have studied the peculiarities of examination of temporary disability

due to nursing a family member; there were specified the criteria of occurrence of temporary disability cases due to nursing the patients of the studied group pursuant to the legal acts and orders of the Russian Federation.

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"This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors."
"Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest."

The sketch of the article has been studied and approved by the authors

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